

COMMUNITY-BASED MARINE
CLIMATE MONITORING

ARCTIC
PASSION

Qaanaaq

PIKIALASORSUAQ SENTINEL GRØNLAND

(Pikialasorsuarmi Nasiffik)

Pikialasorsuaq Sentinel Greenland is a marine and climate-focused monitoring program run in collaboration between local hunters in Pikialasorsuaq, Greenland, and researchers from the Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI) and the Greenland Climate Research Centre at the Greenland Institute of Natural Resources.

Through community meetings and conversations, we identify the data and knowledge needs of local communities that can be investigated using the tools and instruments we have at our disposal. It is important that all measurements and activities we undertake benefit the local community and do not disturb the natural environment. This booklet presents the latest activities and findings. It will be updated every other year.

MONITORING ACTIVITIES

We monitor climate changes and study their effects by measuring changes in sea ice, ocean temperature and salinity, and when narwhals are present in the fjord and at the ice edge. We examine how narwhals are affected by ice and temperature. We also measure underwater soundscape – both natural sounds from ice and marine mammals and man-made noise from small boats and ships. We use silent instruments to measure the fjord's temperature and to record the sounds of narwhals.

SEA ICE IN INGLEFIELD BREDNING

/Kangerlussuaq

The sea ice in Inglefield Bredning follows an annual cycle consisting of the following phases:

SEA ICE: The fjord is covered with and fast sea ice. People travel on the ice using dog sledges, snowmobiles, and even cars along established routes. Seals, walruses, and Greenland halibut are caught through the ice and at the ice edge.

BREAK-UP: The break-up starts in the outer fjord and moves inward toward the glaciers. Narwhal hunting takes place at the ice edge, while seal hunting and halibut fishing continue further inside the fjord.

OPEN WATER: The fjord becomes ice-free to Qeqertat. Narwhal hunting continues, along with hunting for walrus, belugas, and seals.

FREEZING: In autumn, a prolonged freezing period begins, during which the ice can come and go. Travel becomes difficult because the ice is too thin to walk or drive on and too thick to navigate through by boat.

SEA ICE THICKNESS AND SNOW DEPTH ON THE ICE

The sea ice thickness (green graph) grows throughout the winter at a rate of about 1 cm per day during the dark months. Toward April, the growth slows down, and by the end of May, the ice usually reaches its maximum thickness, typically around 100–140 cm.

The ice thickness has been measured south of Qaanaaq every winter in March or April since 2011. Even though the measurements are not taken on the same date each year, they still show that the ice generally reaches about 110 cm in thickness at the end of winter, including in recent years.

Measurements of snow depth (blue graph) on the ice have varied significantly over time. This is not surprising, as we know snow depth can change from hour to hour due to wind packing and drifting. For a single location, as shown in the figure, the data suggest a trend toward more snow in the winter – which aligns with future expectations.

TEMPERATURE STRATIFICATION IN THE FJORD

In Inglefield Bredning, there are several layers of water distinguished by their temperature and salinity.

The warm so-called Atlantic Water flows in from the south year-round (illustrated with a red arrow on the map), at depths of several hundred meters below the colder layers. This Atlantic Water reaches to the front of the marine terminating glaciers.

Above the Atlantic Water, colder polar water layers (blue arrow) spread beneath the sea ice or surface layer.

There are year-to-year differences in how deep and warm these layers are, which affects fish, whales, and the melting of glaciers.

We measure the temperatures and depths of these layers annually.

THE ATLANTIC LAYER

Temperature in the fjord has been measured at fixed locations since 2011. Inglefield Bredning is deep enough for the warm deep current from the North Atlantic, which flows north along the west coast of Greenland, to reach into the fjord.

This current is strongest and warmest at 300–350 meters depth and takes several years to travel north, gradually cooling along the way. Above it are colder water layers formed during the winter or originating from the Arctic. Each year since 2011, the highest winter temperatures have been measured at these depths.

The temperature in the Atlantic Layer varies. A particularly warm period built up toward 2014. From 2015 to 2021, the temperature of the inflowing Atlantic water gradually decreased. Off the coast of Qaanaaq, the temperatures did not exceed 1°C. Since 2021, the heat has returned, but in 2025, we still do not see the same high temperatures off Qaanaaq as in 2014.

Despite being only around 1°C and located at 300 m depth, the warmth in the Atlantic Layer has a significant impact on the fjord. There is enough heat to melt ice from deep glaciers and icebergs, producing meltwater that rises toward the surface due to its lower density. This process is essential for maintaining life in the fjord, especially for plankton and Greenland halibut.

THE DEEP FJORD, 600 M

THE DEEP FJORD IS WARMING

Below the Atlantic Layer, the water is colder and less influenced by external and internal changes in the fjord. These depths are where Greenland halibut are found. Temperature developments at 600 meters depth show a strong inflow and renewal of cold water in 2016 and 2017. Since then, the temperature has steadily increased, and in March 2025 we recorded the highest temperatures in our measurement period.

Worth knowing:

- The seawater in Inglefield Bredning is salty and thus only freezes when cooled below -1.7°C .
- The fjord contains enough heat to melt about 10 meters of sea ice, most of the heat comes from the Atlantic Layer.

DEPTH OF WINTER-COLD WATER UNDER THE ICE (-1.5°C)

WINTER COLD UNDER THE ICE

Under the sea ice, the water temperature is about -1.7°C – the freezing point of salty seawater. This cold layer generally gets deeper as the winter progresses, until about May. In our measurements, we’ve observed significant year-to-year variations in the thickness of this cold layer. Since 2017, the cold layer has not reached below 20–30 meters in depth, but in 2025 we again see near-freezing seawater as deep as 70 meters. This may be a sign that the slow warming trend observed up to 2025 in the deep waters of the fjord is reversing.

SOUND RESEARCH

Whales depend on sound to navigate, find food, stay in contact, and detect other whales and potential threats. The ocean is full of sounds – both natural and man-made. We need to understand these sounds to know whether they affect the lives of whales. Humans cannot hear all underwater sounds. We use computer software to visualise the sound, showing frequency, time, and intensity. **THIS IS CALLED A SPECTROGRAM.**

Sounds are recorded using underwater microphones (hydrophones), which are themselves completely silent. When there are no sound-producing sources nearby, the ocean sounds like a faint hissing – known as background noise. This can be seen on a spectrogram and heard by scanning the QR code with your mobile phone.

SOUND OF THE SEA WITHOUT ANIMALS, BOATS OR ICE NEARBY

FREQUENCIES IN SOUNDS

Different whale species use very different sounds, consisting of different frequencies. The diagram shows examples of a narwhal, a bowhead whale, a fin whale, and a human. Whales can generally hear the same frequencies they produce. When we know which frequencies the animals use, we also know which frequencies might disturb them.

Different boats produce different sounds. The diagram includes the frequencies produced by a cruise ship, a small tanker, a motorboat, and a kayak. Humans produce many different types of sound. Finally, the chart shows the frequencies of a common echo sounder.

A LOGARITHMIC SCALE

Frequencies are displayed in Hertz. There is a huge difference between the high-pitched frequencies used by, for example, narwhals and the low tones used by fin whales. That's why the frequencies are shown on a logarithmic scale.

There are only 9 Hz between the low tones in the figure, but up to 90,000 Hz in the high tones. The blue bars therefore, represent frequency ranges much wider than they appear in the illustration.

NOISE IN THE OCEAN

Man-made sounds:

Man-made underwater noise is often referred to as “pollution.” Underwater, most of this comes from ship traffic, seismic exploration for oil, or seabed mapping. Many boats use devices like echo-sounders to detect fish and measure depth. Some scientific instruments also emit sound to collect echo data from animals or particles in the water. These can be used to measure plankton, fish, and ocean currents. Researchers are careful not to deploy such instruments in areas where they could disturb marine mammals or fisheries.

Sea ice that "sings" and sea ice that cracks

Ice produces many different types of sound. That’s why the Arctic Ocean is a very noisy place. Calving icebergs make loud cracks and bangs. Sea ice rubbing against itself during winter can sound like singing or whistling, or like creaking.

Sea ice that cracks

Sea ice that “sings”

Noise from small boats

ANIMAL SOUNDS

All marine mammals produce sounds typical of their species. Sound is important to them for hunting, finding food, locating mates, and navigation. This also makes them easy to detect with audio recorders. The different animals' sounds are distinct and easy to recognize.

You can listen to the sounds by scanning the QR code with your phone.

RINGED SEAL SONG

BELUGA WHALE SONG

WALRUS KNOCKING AND BELL SOUNDS

NARWHAL ECHOLOCATION AND WHISTLES

NARWHAL SOUNDS

Narwhals use echolocation to “see” underwater – similar to how humans use sonar to locate fish or the seabed. They also use whistles to communicate within their pod. These whistles can be heard by humans. Echolocation consists of a series of short “clicks” across a wide range of frequencies, some of which are so high-pitched that humans cannot hear them. But we can hear the low frequencies of the clicks.

The figure shows narwhal echolocation clicks and whistles in a spectrogram. By scanning the QR code, you can listen to both types of sounds on your mobile.

Worth knowing:

New research suggests that each narwhal has its own, personal whistle. This is also known from many dolphin species and is called a signature whistle. When a narwhal uses its signature whistle, the rest of the pod knows where it is. Researchers are working on using these signature whistles to count the number of narwhals.

NARWHAL ECHOLOCATION NARWHAL WHISTLE

NARWHAL WHISTLE

NARWHAL SOUNDS IN INGLEFIELD BREDNING

(Kangerlussuaq):

We have recorded narwhal sounds in Inglefield Bredning. We take note of the earliest and latest recordings each year. Once we have collected enough years of data, we will be able to identify trends in when narwhals arrive in and leave the fjord.

FIRST NARWHAL RECORDED

2022	17 June
2023	25 June
2024	23 June

Narwhals must come to the surface to breathe, so they only enter the fjord when they can find a breathing hole in the ice. That's why the presence of sea ice is important for the timing of their arrival. This is shown in the figure: The orange rings mark narwhal sound recordings. The blue line shows the distance from the recorder to the ice edge.

Narwhals can swim about 6 km under the ice. So, when the ice edge is more than 6 km away (i.e. when the blue curve is higher), no narwhals are recorded.

POTENTIAL IMPACTS ON GREENLAND HALIBUT FISHERIES

Changes in temperature and fishing both show slow fluctuations. It is not possible to explain changes in fishery yields based on temperature alone. However, temperature does provide insight into expected levels of glacial melt and possibly the strength of Atlantic Water inflow from the south. We observe that fishery yields peaked in 2018 with 250 tons of Greenland halibut landed, four years after the first warm period in the fjord (2014). The new warm period began in 2022 and continues today. If the relationship between temperature and fishing is strong enough, this could indicate improved fishing conditions in the coming years. However, many other factors influence fishery trends and Greenland halibut populations. In general, more species are expected to migrate north as ocean temperatures rise.

On the other hand, our findings show that narwhals depend on the ice edge. This may be because they feed on polar cod, which live under the sea ice in spring, and because they are drawn to the cold, productive waters near glaciers. If the ice disappears for longer periods each year, narwhals may spend more time in the fjord. Since they also eat Greenland halibut, this could impact halibut populations in the future.

In short, it's difficult to predict the future of the fishery, as many different factors may influence it, both positively and negatively.

Local knowledge and an understanding of fjord ecology are essential for interpreting measurements and make future predictions.

PLANNED ACTIVITIES

August 2025: Retrieval of anchored instruments from the seafloor and deployment of new ones

March 2026: Measurements of ice, snow, and ocean temperature from the ice edge to the glaciers

March/April 2026: Deployment of underwater sound recorders

WE HAVE RECEIVED REQUESTS FROM LOCAL COMMUNITY MEMBERS FOR FUTURE ACTIVITIES:

- Measure noise from tourist ships
- Investigate whether genetically distinct types of narwhals visit the areas around Siorapaluk, Qaanaaq, and Savissivik

Always welcome to contact us

We are always happy to speak with locals, whether to hear interesting observations or to investigate questions through scientific methods.

When in Qaanaaq, we are based at the DMI station. You can contact Aksel Ascanius, who can forward a message to us, or reach out directly:

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Our measurements and data would not exist without collaboration. **THANK YOU** to:
Aksel Ascanius, Peter Avike, Rasmus Avike, Qillaq Danielsen, Carl Bror Isaksen, Hans Jensen, Lars Jeremiassen, Naduk N. Kristensen, Olennguaq Kristensen, Gedion Kristiansen, Mamarut Kristiansen, Mikile Kristiansen, Quma Kvist, Niels Miunge, Else Ostermann, Kim Petersen, Tukummeq Qaaviaq, Qalaseq Sadorana, Gustav Simigaq, Paulus Simigaq and many more.

Danish
Meteorological
Institute

ARCTIC
PASSION

ARCTIC PASSION PS7

- Community based Monitoring for Arctic Marine Climate Change,
Noise Pollution and Impacts on Marine Living Resources

PUBLISHED BY: ARCTIC PASSION

TEXT: MALENE SIMON HEGELUND AND STEFFEN MALSKÆR OLSEN

PHOTOS: STEFFEN MALSKÆR OLSEN, MALENE SIMON HEGELUND,
CHRISTIAN SØLBECK, AND CARSTEN EGEVANG, PINNGORTITALERIFFIK

LAYOUT: INUVA

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